

PREDICTION OF NON-MECHANICAL TRANSIENT STRAINS
IN POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES
Ernest G. Wolff
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Oregon State University
Corvallis, OR 97331-6001

ABSTRACT

A model was developed to predict the transient strains which occur when a carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite is subjected to a new thermal or chemical environment. It is used here to determine the coefficient of in-plane moisture expansion (CME or $\Delta L/L$ per % moisture content) during transverse (Fickian) diffusion. Moisture induced weight changes follow straight line relationships when plotted against the theoretical fractional weight change G , which varies from 0 to 1 (when $t = \infty$). However, moisture (and/or thermal) gradients are superimposed on the ply layup, and hence on stiffness variations. This model uses standard laminate codes to calculate the strains and curvatures (E_0-x , E_0-y , E_0-xy , $K-x$, $K-y$, and $K-xy$) in the presence of moisture gradients. The effects of ply parameters on CME and results for plates and tubes are presented.

KEYWORDS: Absorption; Environmental Effects; Stability; Testing

1. INTRODUCTION

In classical laminated plate (CLP) computer codes, expansion or shrinkage accompanying changes in absorbed moisture is analogous to temperature induced strain; thus, a moisture load is equivalent to a thermal load. The coefficients of linear moisture and thermal expansion are defined in a similar manner:

$$\text{CME} = \beta_{ij} = e_{ij}^m / \Delta M \quad (1)$$

$$\text{CTE} = \alpha_{ij} = e_{ij}^T / \Delta T \quad (2)$$

where e_{ij} are the induced strains and M denotes the percent moisture content. ΔM equals $(W - W_0)/pV = \Delta C/p$, where W is the weight of the sample, p the density, V the volume, and C the concentration of moisture. Unlike the temperature situation, moisture equilibration may only be assumed after prolonged storage, but seldom during use. A model for the prediction of in-plane laminate strains during transverse moisture changes was proposed earlier (1). The CME of a laminate was the product of a time varying integral function based on the fractional moisture content and a stiffness function for each ply. It was assumed that the single ply CME is not a function of moisture content. The present paper generalizes this model and shows how a CLP may be used to predict time dependent strains.

2. THEORY

The CME consists of two parts, a concentration/weight or % moisture change and a strain change. The former is readily determined by weighing the sample after exposure to a new moisture environment. The change in moisture concentration (the moisture load) is then given by:

$$\Delta C = C_0 - C_{av} \quad (3)$$

where C_0 is the initial (uniform) concentration and C_{av} is the average moisture concentration in the entire sample after some time "t". In the absence of diffusion along fiber/matrix interfaces, cracks or voids, and at moderate times and temperatures, one can assume Fickian diffusion applies. The instantaneous concentration then is (2);

$$C(z,t) = 1 - C_0 (4/\pi) \sum [1/(2n+1)] \sin [\pi (2n+1) (z/h)] \exp \{-[(2n+1)(\pi/h)]^2 Dt\} \quad (4)$$

where h is the sample thickness and D the diffusivity in the transverse (z) direction. The fractional change in total moisture content is the integral of $C(z,t)$ with respect to distance z or

$$G = (C_0 - C_{av}) / (C_0 - C_{av}) \quad (5)$$

$$= 1 - (8/\pi^2) \sum [1/(2n+1)^2] \exp \{-[(2n+1) (\pi/h)]^2 Dt\} \quad (6)$$

An analytical approximation for G has been given by Shen and Springer (3);

$$G = 1 - \exp \{-7.3 (Dt/h^2)^{0.75}\} \quad (7)$$

The average concentration over a range of z may also be expressed in terms of the error function for short times (2). Thus

$$C_{av} = 1 - (C_0/h) \int_0^h \text{erf} [(z/2) (Dt)^{-1/2}] dz \quad (8)$$

Equation 5 shows that ΔC is proportional to G . Thus the weight change plotted against the right hand side of Eqs. 6 or 7 should yield a straight line. Then measurements over limited times can be extrapolated to $G = 1$ (where $t = \infty$) to give the uniform moisture content change. Figure 1 shows that Eq. 7 gives good agreement with the exact solution of Eq. 6 ($D = 6e^{-7} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ and $h = 0.508 \text{ mm}$).

FIGURE 1. Predicted Fractional Moisture Content Changes. The exact relation (Eq. 6) (•) compared to the Shen and Springer Approximation (Eq. 7) (Δ).

3. STRAIN ANALYSIS

A CLP code (such as SQ5, (4)) applies the same moisture (ΔC) load to each ply of the laminate. Then the moisture induced mid-plane strain in the x direction of a laminate is;

$$e_{o-x} = f (\Delta C * \beta_{11}, \Delta C * \beta_{22}) \quad (9)$$

where the subscripts "11" and "22" refer to the fiber and transverse directions of a single ply, respectively. As long as these products remain constant, the calculated e_{o-x} (or e_{o-y}) will remain unchanged. Since a point stress CLP code calls for only a single moisture (or thermal) load input, we must consider that each ply (j) has a variable β_{ij} depending on the ratio of

its average moisture concentration C_j to the laminate average concentration C_{av} . Thus at any given time;

$$\beta_{ij} = \beta_k [(C_o - C_n) / (C_o - C_{av})] \quad (10)$$

The subscript "k" refers to either "11" or "22", and "n" refers to the individual ply in the laminate. For example, one might refer to the innermost plies of an 8-ply mid-plane symmetric laminate as $n = 1$ and the outermost plies as $n = 4$. After diffusion starts, each ply will have a different set of β_{ij} at each time. Hence a CLP code treats each ply (n) as a different material, with all properties the same except for the β input values. Equations 3, 5, and 10 may be combined to show that for absorption, where $C_o = 0$,

$$\beta_{ij} = \beta_k C_n (G C_o)^{-1} \quad (11)$$

The average C_n value for each ply may be calculated in two ways. First we take the average of the ply boundary concentrations, as calculated by Eq. 4. Alternatively, Eq. 8 can be used to give the average concentration, and this is found to be more accurate if the concentration gradient in the ply deviates considerably from linearity. The choice of method is guided by the agreement between the totalled average concentration of all the plies and the overall C_{av} from Eq. 6.

Figure 2 shows the effective β_{ij} values from Eq. 11 for absorption by a four ply laminate with nominal $\beta_{11} = 6 \times 10^{-5}/\%M$ and $\beta_{22} = 4.5 \times 10^{-3}/\%M$ (1,5). With desorption, Eq. 10 becomes:

$$\beta_{ij} = \beta_k (C_o - C_n) (G C_o)^{-1} \quad (12)$$

Equations 11 and 12 are equivalent as long as $C_o = C_{\infty}$, and the diffusivities are the same for both processes. The C_n curves are simply reversed. The approach is then as follows: a) Find the average moisture content in each ply as a function of time (Eq. 4 or 8). b) The effective β_{ij} are determined for each ply as a function of time (Eq. 11 or 12). c) The laminate is analyzed as if each ply were a material differing only in its values of β_{11} and β_{22} . e) The in-plane strains are determined at each time and plotted against the fractional change in strain (G).

4. ANALYTICAL RESULTS

4.1 Microstrain versus Fractional Moisture Change A CLP code shows that the CME increases with β_{11} , β_{22} , E_{22} , ν_{12} and decreases with E_{11} . G_{12} has little effect. Figure 3 uses the effective values of β to predict the in-plane, 0° strain of four ply laminates of T300/5208 when exposed to 0.8 wt% equilibrium moisture change after complete dryout. Ply properties are $E_{11} = 26.25$ msi,

FIGURE 2. Effective β_{11} and β_{22} Variation with Fractional Moisture Content Change G .

FIGURE 3. Predicted 0° In-Plane Strain for T300/5208 Four-Ply Layups. (Δ) 90/0/0/90 and (\bullet) 0/90/90/0

$E_{22} = 1.49$ msi, $\nu_{12} = 0.28$ and $G_{12} = 1.04$ msi. It is seen that there is divergence from a straight line plot in the predicted strains in the case of the relatively low modulus T300/5208 system when the ply orientations on the outside have the maximum effective β differences (0° versus 90°). Thus, extrapolation of the experimental curves from $G = 0.75$ to $G = 1$ by a straight line will not give accurate values of the equilibrium strain.

4.2 Effect of Fiber Stiffness Figure 4 shows absorption by four ply layups with a stiffer fiber (P75/934) system. Ply properties are $E_{11} = 40$ msi, $E_{22} = 0.9$ msi, $\nu_{12} = 0.3$, and $G_{12} = 0.7$ msi. As the stiffness of the plies increases the divergence of Fig. 3 decreases. Figure 4 also shows that since the mixed cross-ply/angle ply layups are not mid-plane symmetric, there is a divergence of equilibrium strains. (Eight ply symmetric layups here would all have the same ultimate strain (about $148 \mu\text{in/in}$). CME measurements of such laminates need to take into account the expected plate curvature. It can be shown that the divergence between curves for the $90/0/\pm 45$ and $0/90/\pm 45$ layups for the gradient versus uniform moisture distribution is on the same order of magnitude as the divergence between the two center curves in Figure 4 - about $3-6 \mu\epsilon$. In an 8-ply symmetric case, the divergence further decreases and all $\pi/4$ family of layups give the same equilibrium values.

FIGURE 4. Predicted 0° In-Plane Strain versus Fractional Moisture Change for P75/934 Plates with 4-ply Layups. (□) 0/90/45/-45 (○) 90/0/0/90 (Δ) 0/90/90/0 (●) 90/0/45/-45

4.3 Effect of Temperature A change in diffusivity alters both the gradient (β_{ij}) values from ply to ply and the moisture load (Eq. 3) at a given time. Since these quantities change together, the present model indicates no net alteration of the shape of the strain versus G curve. The diffusivity needed to plot strain data against the correct G value is determined from the initial slope of the measured weight change (3).

5. EXPERIMENTAL

CME measurements on composite materials require measurements of strain and weight at constant temperature and humidity under well defined diffusion conditions. Thin walled tubes and flat panel laminates edges were sealed with a silicone coated polyester tape (Airtech "Flashbreaker"). Linear variable differential transducers (LVDTs) with a sensitivity of 0.8 mm/ volt were bonded to low CTE glass-ceramic (Schott "Zerodur") blocks via a low outgassing filled epoxy adhesive (Varian TORR-SEAL). A Zerodur reference detects discontinuities due to vibrations, and LVDT temperature and voltage instabilities. A differential strain accuracy of about $\pm 2 \mu\text{m/m}$ was achieved. To avoid temperature excursions of the LVDTs, weight change samples were maintained in an identical oven. Both sets of data are plotted against G, extrapolated to $G = 1$ and the ratio gives the CME.

6. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Typical results for CFRP plates (6-8) can be interpreted with the present model. The 0° desorption strain was investigated for two thin wall, 0.1524 m long with 0.0673 m diameter, four ply tubes of P75/930 material, with layups 0/90/90/0 and 90/0/+45/-45. Figure 5 shows that the desorption strains at 65°C after equilibration at 50% relative humidity for the 90/0/+45/-45 layup are initially less than those of the 0/90/90/0 for which a straight line is obtained on a plot against G ($D = 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$). The ultimate values are similar for both tubes ($80 \mu\text{m/m}$) and the measured ΔM of 0.71%. The results indicate that β_{11} and β_{22} were $30 \times 10^{-6}/\%M$ and $4.25 \times 10^{-3}/\%M$, respectively, well within the reported range (1,6). These layups, if mid-plane symmetric, would all have the same CME. The tube configuration promotes this by restraining the normal out-of-plane curvature of a 90/0/ ± 45 plate layup.

FIGURE 5. Measured Desorption Strains for Four-Ply P75/930 Tubes at 65°C.
 $(D = 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s})$ - - - 0/90/90/0 _____ 90/0/45/-45

7. DISCUSSION

Measurement of the CME is nominally based on the Fickian diffusion model where weight change is proportional to G . The model proposed helps to interpret deviations from a straight line relation due to low values of E_f , short times (low G) and/or a small number of plies. The experimental results also confirm that a tubular configuration will modify results predicted from CLP codes in the case of unsymmetrical laminate, due to restriction of plate curvatures.

Deviations of the moisture induced strain from a straight line relationship with G may also be due to: a) changing residual stresses, b) stress dependence of the diffusivity, c) moisture content induced stiffness changes, d) voids, and e) viscoelastic effects.

Work by Henson and Weitsman (9) indicated that the boundary layer material acquires an increasingly compressive state during absorption but tensile during desorption due to moisture induced matrix swelling. After curing, the transverse residual stresses in the 0° and 90° layers of a 0/90/90/0 layup are tensile, the axial stresses are compressive. Addition of moisture causes swelling in the transverse direction; this will decrease the tensile stresses and presumably decrease both the transverse and the through-thickness diffusivities. Consequently, absorption may be slower than desorption.

Tensile stresses perpendicular to the fiber direction raise the moisture saturation levels, accentuate the asymmetries between absorption and desorption, and promote deviations from pure Fickian diffusion (9). Constant transverse tensile stresses accentuated the trend of initially slower absorption, with later slower desorption. An increase in the deviatoric tensile stress in the direction of the flux increases the rate of sorption (10).

Moisture added to voids will not contribute to swelling, but only to weight changes (11). E_{22} and G_{12} may decrease by about 10% between dry and saturation in water (100% R.H.)(11). E_{11} decreases by 4% and Poisson's ratio increases by 13% (for AS/3501-5). The present work involved stiffer fibers and changes of about 50% R.H., thus the analysis would require only gradual changes of 2-3% in these lamina input properties.

Viscoelastic stress relaxation, which would reduce the difference between ab- and desorption curves, is likely to be significant only at higher moisture contents. There is interest in comparing desorption in vacuo to dry air or flowing inert gas. Due to boundary layer effects the rates of equilibration might change, but it is doubtful that CME values would be altered.

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9. REFERENCES

1. E.G. Wolff and S.A. Eselun, Conference on Advanced Composites - Special Topics, Technology Conferences, El Segundo, CA, 1979.
2. W. Jost, Diffusion in Solids, Liquids and Gases Academic Press, 1952.
3. C.H. Shen and G.S. Springer, J. Comp. Mat., 10, 2 (1976).
4. D.L. Reed, "Point Stress Laminate Analysis" General Dynamics/Fort Worth Report FZM-5494, April 1970.
5. E.G. Wolff in S.M. Lee, ed., International Encyclopedia of Composites - 4, VCH Publishers, Inc., 1991, p. 279.
6. E.G. Wolff, "Dimensional Stability," SPIE, 1335, 70 (1990).
7. C. Blair and J. Zakrzewski, SPIE, 1303 (1990).
8. C. Blair and J. Zakrzewski, SAMPE International Symposium, 22, 918 (1990).
9. M.C. Henson and Y. Weitsman, Composites '86: Recent Advances in Japan and the United States, Japan-US, CCM-III, 775 (1986).

10. D.C. Ruhmann and E.M. Wu, The Effect of Stress on Diffusion in Composites - Experimental Observations, Monsanto/Washington Report HPC-73-162, Contract N00014-67-C-0218, ARPA Order 876 February (1974).
11. H.T. Hahn and R.Y. Kim, ASTM-STP-658, 98 (1977).

10. BIOGRAPHY

Ernest G. Wolff (B.Sc., M.I.T., and Ph.D, Imperial College, London) is Associate Professor in the Mechanical Engineering Department of Oregon State University and also chief consultant to Precision Measurements & Instruments, Inc., whose specialty is CME and CTE testing. Formerly at Northrop and The Aerospace Corporation, Dr. Wolff's research has been on the dimensional stability of materials.